
FACEBOOK USAGE AND ITS EFFECTS ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE SECOND YEAR FCIC COLLEGE STUDENTS

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FACEBOOK USAGE AND ITS EFFECTS ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE SECOND YEAR FCIC COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Facebook is one of the social media platforms that most students have been using to connect with their family, and friends and even to share ideas that could be useful in their academic. However, Facebook also has a big impact on the academic performance of the students which might affect their academic performance. Therefore, this study aims to determine the effect of Facebook Usage on the Academic Performance of FCIC 2nd Year students. To achieve the aim of this study, a research questionnaire was used as the main instrument to gather data which was distributed to 131 second-year college students of FCIC which was randomly picked. A research questionnaire was used as an instrument to support the quantitative design and the collected data in this study will be critically analyzed so that we will know the effects of Facebook usage on the academic performance of the FCIC 2nd year college students. According to the results, 58% out of 100% agreed that Facebook is useful to their studies. Nevertheless, 77% of our respondents answered “YES” that Facebook is a disturbance to their studies. Furthermore, numerous answered that Facebook is not able to support their studies but there are some states that Facebook will be useful too in their studies through sharing of ideas.

Keywords: *Facebook, Academic Performance, Facebook Usage*

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INTRODUCTION

When the pandemic arises, young people spend more time socializing and doing group studies online. Social media sites saw an increase of 61% in web traffic compared to the typical rates during the Covid-19 outbreak. Social Media is a medium of communication that enables teachers and students to communicate through numerous online learning platforms (Vordos et al.,2020). As students became more focused on social networking several researchers conducted a study about the impact of social media that might affect students' academic performance. One of the most social media apps that most students use is FACEBOOK.

Facebook is a social networking service originally launched as “FACEMASH” on October 28, 2003, before changing its name to “FACEBOOK” on February 4, 2004. It was founded by Mark Zuckerberg and his fellow college roommates Eduardo Savesin, Andrew McCollum, Dustin Moskovitz, and Chris Huges who were students at Harvard University. The platform was made available for High School students and to the public in the year 2006 (History of Facebook,12 February 2006). Facebook is the most widely held and popular social network site among students, as shown in the study by Nielsen (2011).

Furthermore, social media is viewed as a distraction and leads students to procrastinate in the fulfillment of their academic responsibilities. However, other students insist that using social media during class is the way to ease the boredom they feel in college. The more the students spend more time on using Facebook, the less time was spent on educational programs (Kirschner and Karpinski.,2010). In this study, we, aim to spread awareness to the students of Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception to have an idea and be aware of how Facebook usage might affect their academic performance.

Based on many theories and the information acquired, Facebook became widely known to everyone. The goal of this study is to know the effects of Facebook usage on the academic performance of FCIC 2nd Year College students. The researchers tackled this idea because students nowadays are fond of spending their time using Facebook. This study will be conducted to determine how students will gain knowledge and awareness of the effect of Facebook Usage on their Academic Performance.

In addition, this study will help students to be aware of the possible effects of spending time using Facebook that might affect or might improve their academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

For all we know, Facebook is one of the most famous social media sites nowadays. It helps us connect to everyone and everywhere in just one click. But are we using Facebook properly? So, this study aims to give awareness and knowledge on the possible effects of Facebook usage on the Academic performance of the 2nd Year FCIC College Students. The findings and results of this study involve a thorough discussion. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions.

1. What are the possible effects of Facebook on the FCIC 2nd year college students?
2. What are the Pros and Cons of Facebook usage on the Academic Performance of the students?
3. How does the usage of Facebook affect their Academic Performance?

METHODOLOGY

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay Leyte, Incorporated, Baybay City. FCIC is a Catholic school composed of the Basic Education, Senior High School, and College Departments.

The respondents of this study will be the 2nd Year College Students, randomly picked in the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay City, Leyte. There will be 131 respondents in the 2nd year College students.

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Year Level	Course	Population	Sample Size
2 nd Year	BSCrim	50	30
	BSOA & BSIT	40	20
	BSED & ACT	46	26
	BSHM & BSBA	42	27
	BEED & DM	40	28
Total		218	131

Instrumentation

The researchers used a survey questionnaire in this study as a guide in interpreting, analyzing, and measuring the data to be collected. By this method, data were gathered according to the answers of the respondents and adopted appropriately for gaining the insights and the needed data for the study.

Research Design

This research study is correlative research that investigates, measures, and describes one or more aspects. The research study is about Facebook Usage and Its Effect on the Academic Performance of FCIC 2nd Year College Students. A total of 131 students participated in a survey through a given questionnaire.

Gathering of Data

The researchers randomly chose students to answer the given questionnaire. The researchers guided them on how to answer the questionnaire to attain the list of objectives regarding this study.

In this study, we used the percentage technique to get the average score of each question and the total number of respondents. The formula that is used in this study is:

$$P=f/n \times 100$$

P = Percentage of responses to each option

f = Total number of the answer of the respondents

n = total number of respondents

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results based on the objectives of the study. It discusses and interprets the data gathered that will help treat and find the answer to the problem, of Facebook usage and its effects on the academic performance of the 2nd year college students.

Table 2: Usefulness of Facebook to studies

Choices	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes	55	42
No	76	58
Total	131	100

Table 2 shows the results of the answer to the said question. Based on the table, out of 131 respondents, 55 students answered “yes” that Facebook is useful to their studies, and a percentage of 42%. While 76 of the respondents answered “no” that Facebook is not useful to their studies that consists of 58% with an overall total of 100%. Therefore, the majority of the respondents believe that Facebook is not useful to their studies.

Table 3: Facebook as a disturbance to studies

Choices	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes	101	77
No	30	23
Total	131	100

Table 3 shows the total number and percentage of the students' responses to the given question about Facebook as a disturbance to their studies. The 101 respondents who said "yes" made up 77% of the participants in the research's whole population, while the 30 respondents who indicated "no" took approximately 23%. Therefore, a large number of respondents believed that Facebook is a disturbance to their studies.

Table 4. Facebook usage during class hours

Choices	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes	40	31
No	91	69
Total	131	100

Table 4 states the total number of respondents who indicated they use Facebook while attending class. According to the data, 31% of respondents claimed they used Facebook during their class, whereas 69% of respondents said no. Therefore, some of the respondents used Facebook to attend their classes.

Table 5: Reasons of Facebook Usage

Choices	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Reduces Stress	62	47
Gaming	18	14
Disseminate Information	47	36
Communication	120	92
Academic Purposes	34	26
Total	281	214

Table 5 shows the reasons of the respondents why they are using Facebook the respondents may check more than one option. Based on the table, gaming has the lowest percentage at just 14%, whereas communication has a higher rate at 92%.

Given that respondents selected more than one option, the percentage was higher than 100%.

Table 6: Cons of Facebook in relation to Studies

Choices	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Lack of focus	95	73
Lack of sleep	93	71
Results of Failing Grades	18	14
Total	206	158

Table 6 shows the cons of Facebook in relation to the studies of the respondents. It shows that 73% of people selected a lack of focus, followed by a lack of sleep with 71%, while only 14% selected failing grades as the outcome. Since respondents chose several choices, the percentage exceeded 100%.

Table 7: Hours spent on Using Facebook

Number of hours	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1-2 hours	45	35
2-5 hours	66	50
7-8 hours	20	15
Total	131	100

In table 7, it shows the number of hours that the respondents spend in using Facebook. Table 5 shows that 66 (or 50% of the population) of the respondents spend most of their time on Facebook between two and five hours each day. And 20 (15%) of the respondents frequently use Facebook for seven to eight hours.

Table 8: Midterm Average Range

Midterm Average Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.0 -1.5	25	19
1.6 – 2.0	71	54
2.1 – 2.5	29	22
2.6 – 3.0	2	2
Total	127	97

Table 8 shows the midterm average range of the 2nd year college respondents. The majority of respondents, approximately 54% of the population, have grades between 1.6 and 2.0. The average grade range for 19% of the participants is between 1.0 and 1.5, and for 22%,

it is between 2.1 and 2.5. Only 2% of respondents shared the lowest grades, which fall within the range of 2.6-3.0. Moreover, 3% of the respondents chose not to respond to any of the options.

Table 9: Students affected by any of these on Facebook

Choices	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Stalking	82	63
Bullying	35	27
Discrimination	31	24
Black Mail	4	3
Total	152	117

Table 9 shows if the respondents have been affected by any of the choices given by the researchers. The percentages for stalking are 63%, bullying is 27%, discrimination is 24%, and blackmail is 3%. As a result, stalking got more than half of the responses in total, while blackmail got the least. Due to respondents' multiple selections, the percentage was higher than 100%.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

The study was conducted in Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay Leyte, Incorporated, Baybay City, Leyte, a Catholic institution. There were 218 2nd year College students but we only got 131 of the students' population as our respondents for this study.

The main purpose of this study was to know the effects of Facebook usage on the Academic Performance of the 2nd Year College Students which gave us a clear view of the said study.

The study employed the Correlative design, using a survey questionnaire to fulfill the above aims of the study. Which helped us to interpret the data critically.

Results of the study revealed that the 2nd year College Students of FCIC are not affected by their academic performance because some students state that somewhat Facebook helps them with their communication skills and updates to online activities. However, interpreting the data that we have, the majority of the respondents answered that Facebook is a disturbance to their studies which indicates that Facebook usage harms their studies because of lack of sleep that will eventually result having a lack of focus which results in failing grades and that will lead to a poor academic performance.

Conclusion

The result of the study showed that the effect of using Facebook on the Academic performance of the 2nd year College students in FCIC is negative because based on the data that we have gathered they are distracted and don't have focus because of too much exposure to Facebook. However, there are also positive impacts on studies in such a way that they could communicate and be updated on any school activities.

That's why, Facebook is not that negative to the students' academic performance. It also helps them in any way to improve their academic performance. Engaging in Facebook is not a problem if we are responsible for our actions.

Recommendations

Given the information with regards to Facebook usage and Its Effects on the Academic Performance of the 2nd Year College FCIC students, and after a thorough analysis, interpretation, and conclusion the following recommendations are stated:

- Students should limit their level of Facebook exposure and they should be responsible enough to handle and face the consequences of using too much on Facebook.
- Students should be aware of the Pros and Cons of Facebook that might affect their academic performance negatively and positively.
- Parents and teachers should assess their learners in using Facebook so that they will be guided accordingly on the sites and apps they're engaging in.
- Future researchers should work on scholarly crafted research so that others may find our work credible and valuable to other researchers and that we may also help them gain more knowledge and insights that could be useful to their studies as well.

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